

ANALYSIS OF MECHANISMS TO SUPPORT THE AGRICULTURAL SECTOR IN THE CREATION OF PUBLIC GOODS

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Abstract

The agricultural sector creates public goods that are an integral part of the image of each region. Improving the supply of public goods increases the attractiveness of the region and requires an approach for support, taking into account regional specificities. The regional approach is distinguished by the fact that use and develop local resources, and thus be utilized to the fullest extent the capabilities of the policy on rural development to realize their goals. On the other hand between the mechanisms of influence, there are differences in terms of their potential and in their implementation. Support for local farmers improve the attractiveness of the area as a place to live and creates an incentive for the overall development of the local society.

The purpose of this article is to establish the potential of the selected mechanisms to support the agricultural sector in the creation of public goods.

The survey results show very large differences in the potential of the studied mechanisms. This determines the inability to balance the effects of their implementation in the context of territorial development. For this purpose it is necessary to develop and test scenarios, which are based on potential mechanisms for stimulating the creation of public goods and to achieve synergistic effects at regional level.

Keywords: rural areas, water protection, food security, agri-environmental schemes, AHP method

Abstrakt

Der Agrarsektor schafft öffentliche Güter, die ein integraler Bestandteil des Images jeder Region sind. Die Verbesserung des Angebots an öffentlichen Gütern erhöht die Attraktivität der Region und erfordert einen Ansatz zur Unterstützung, der die regionalen Besonderheiten berücksichtigt. Der regionale Ansatz zeichnet sich dadurch aus, dass die lokalen Ressourcen genutzt und entwickelt werden und somit die Möglichkeiten der Politik zur ländlichen Entwicklung zur Verwirklichung ihrer Ziele voll ausgeschöpft werden. Auf der anderen Seite gibt es Unterschiede zwischen den Einflußmechanismen, sowohl was ihr Potential als auch was ihre Umsetzung betrifft. Die Unterstützung der lokalen Bauern verbessert die Attraktivität des Gebiets als Lebensraum und schafft einen Anreiz für die Gesamtentwicklung der lokalen Gesellschaft.

Der Zweck dieses Artikels ist es, das Potential der ausgewählten Mechanismen zur Unterstützung des Agrarsektors bei der Schaffung öffentlicher Güter zu ermitteln.

Die Umfrageergebnisse zeigen sehr große Unterschiede im Potential der untersuchten Mechanismen. Dies bestimmt die Unfähigkeit, die Auswirkungen ihrer Umsetzung im Rahmen der territorialen Entwicklung auszugleichen. Zu diesem Zweck ist es notwendig, Szenarien zu entwickeln und zu testen, die auf potenziellen Mechanismen zur Förderung der Schaffung öffentlicher Güter und zur Erzielung von Synergieeffekten auf regionaler Ebene beruhen.

Stichworte: ländliche Gebiete, Wasserschutz, Ernährungssicherheit, Agrar-Umweltmaßnahmen, AHP-Methode

Résumé

Le secteur agricole crée des biens publics qui font partie intégrante de l'image de chaque région. L'amélioration de l'offre de biens publics augmente l'attractivité de la région et nécessite une approche de soutien qui tienne compte des spécificités régionales. L'approche régionale se distingue par le fait qu'elle utilise et développe les ressources locales, et donc qu'elle utilise au maximum les capacités de la politique de développement rural pour atteindre ses objectifs. D'autre part, entre les mécanismes d'influence, il existe des différences en termes de potentiel et de mise en œuvre. Le soutien aux agriculteurs locaux améliore l'attractivité de la région en tant que lieu de vie et crée une incitation au développement global de la société locale.

L'objectif de cet article est d'établir le potentiel des mécanismes sélectionnés pour soutenir le secteur agricole dans la création de biens publics.

Les résultats de l'enquête montrent de très grandes différences dans le potentiel des mécanismes étudiés. Cela détermine l'incapacité à équilibrer les effets de leur mise en œuvre dans le contexte du développement territorial. À cette fin, il est nécessaire d'élaborer et de tester des scénarios basés sur les mécanismes potentiels de stimulation de la création de biens publics et de réaliser des effets synergiques au niveau régional.

Mots clés: zones rurales, protection de l'eau, sécurité alimentaire, programmes agroenvironnementaux, méthode AHP

Agriculture is an important part of socio-economic development of rural areas. Agriculture is seen not only as an opportunity for economic activity but also as a source of public goods that create a unique image of each area. The use and development of local conditions is a prerequisite for the expansion of overall economic activity in the region, which improves the vitality of the local community (Dirimanova, 2013). It should be recognized that between regions there are major differences in terms of their potential and trends of development (Stoeva and Marinov, 2015).

Primary means to influence these processes is the policy of rural development. Within it there are different mechanisms in supporting farmers through its activities to provide public goods. Nowadays support mechanisms are recognized as a means to overcome the negative socio-economic trends that result from market signals (Dimitrova and Dimitrov, 2017). The modern market is very dynamic and in order to meet market requirements often have to be compromised relating mainly to the preservation of natural resources. On the other hand, the market creates opportunities, but their use requires additional

investments that can not be provided by small farms having limited capacity. Targeted support of these farms maintain and develop agriculture in rural areas, improving the environment and becomes a territory attractive for the development of other economic activities such as tourism (Dirimanova, 2013). It also improves the overall image of the region as a provider of public goods.

The purpose of this article is to establish the potential of the selected mechanisms to support the agricultural sector in the creation of public goods.

The object of analysis are support mechanisms concerning the three main public goods for local development (see Table. 1). The factors which determine their applicability.

Table 1. Main public goods supplied by agriculture and governance mechanisms to support them.

Source: Own research, 2018

public goods	governance mechanisms
Water quality and availability	Water protection
Food Security	Local, traditional foods
Scenery and Recreation	Agro-environmental schemes

The study was done in Smolyan, which is typical of a region rich to public goods that are under the influence of agricultural activities. Use the method of data collection focus group and was attended by 10 persons from various stakeholders (farmers, consultants, residents, tourists).

The analysis used a set of criteria and mechanisms that are based on previous research within the project PROVIDE.

For data analysis using comparative analysis and the method AHP /analytics hierarchy process/, by analyzing the potential of each mechanism and determine the score (level of importance) of indicators for the implementation of mechanisms (Hallowell, 2005; Forman and Gass 2001). The rating of the indicators is formed based on the summary score for each municipality calculated by the following formula.

$$A_j = \sum_{i=1}^n B_{ij} \times D_{ij}$$

Where:

A_j - Summary of the facility "j"

B_{ij} - assessment criterion (indicator) "i" mechanism "j"

D_{ij} - weighting coefficient of criterion (indicator) "i" mechanism "j"

n - number of evaluated criteria (indicators)

The weighting factor (D) of each criterion for this mechanism is defined as the ratio between the assessment criteria for the mechanism and the sum of scores for all criteria. Thus determines the share of each criterion in research mechanism.

The evaluation of the criterion (B) for each assembly is determined by the views of the participants in the focus group. Through this technique is defined aggregate (average) assessment criteria.

Results

For each mechanism to support public goods, persons participating in the focus group identified what are its main strengths and weaknesses and to identify opportunities and threats it faces. Thus, for each assembly were measured at 12 criteria whose summary evaluations are presented in Figures 1, 2 and 3.

Figure 1. Importance of factors identified in the SWOT analysis of governance mechanism "Water quality improvements". Source: Own research, 2018

Figure 2. Importance of factors identified in the SWOT analysis of governance mechanism "Food security". Source: Own research, 2018

Figure 3. Importance of factors identified in the SWOT analysis of governance mechanism "Agro-environmental schemes". Source: Own research, 2018

Based on the data presented for each criterion are calculated average score and the weighting factor for the respective assembly / see table. 2 /. Mechanism "Water Management" as the most important strength, the effectiveness of the costs associated with the implementation of mechanisms is, while this criterion was rated highest. It is noteworthy that all three strengths of the mechanism receiving high average scores (over 7), indicating that the mechanism has internal potential. In addition to this statement are set low scores on the weaknesses of the mechanism. However, when evaluating stand low scores of opportunities relating to this mechanism, which limits its potential for implementation. Still high estimates of criteria related to the threats defined

Mechanism "Protection of local, traditional food" all strengths are defined as comparable in order of importance and at the same time appreciate. The average scores were above 8, indicating that the mechanism has considerable domestic potential. In contrast to findings from two weaknesses "Access to Information" and "lack of cooperation" were evaluated with high marks, which reduces the overall potential of the mechanism. However, when evaluating stand higher marks opportunities than threats, which indicates that the mechanism is acknowledged as a means of realizing opportunities and developing local businesses.

Mechanism "Agri" three strengths are defined as relatives in order of importance. Also noticed that they receive higher average scores (over 7), indicating that the mechanism has considerable domestic potential. In addition to this statement are set low scores on the weaknesses of the mechanism.

And under this facility as at the first stand low scores opportunities, which limits the potential mechanism for their realization. Still high estimates of criteria related to the threats determine that mechanism "Agri" can be used as a means to overcome the identified threats and achieve better conditions for business development.

Table 2. Assessment of governance mechanisms support public goods. Source: Own research, 2018

Group	criteria	weight	average score
Water protection			
Strengths	Cost Effectiveness	0.39	8.3
	Easy monitoring	0.25	7.5
	Focus	0.36	7.8
Weaknesses	No account local specificities	0.35	7.2
	Short-term horizon	0.38	5.5
	Unertain effect	0.27	4.3
Possibilities	Synergy	0.38	5.6
	Public support	0.33	5.5
	Shared interest	0.29	6.6
Threats	Limited application	0.34	7.9
	Incompatibility with other objectives	0.32	7.7
	Opportunism	0.34	6.8
Protection of local, traditional foods			
Strengths	Traceability	0.31	8.1
	Small local farm	0.33	8.6
	Traditional local products	0.36	8.5
Weaknesses	Adult farmers without successors	0.28	6.2
	Lack of cooperation	0.34	7.7
	Access to credit and information	0.38	8.5
Opportunities	Higher prices	0.31	6.5
	Demand of healthy local food	0.38	7.5
	Ecommerce	0.31	6.4
Threats	Climate change	0.38	5.4
	Regulations (standards)	0.30	5.8
	Lack of market infrastrucutre (short chain, roads)	0.32	5.9
Agro-environmental schemes			
Strengths	Cost Effectiveness	0.35	8.7
	Soil functionality	0.33	7.6
	Biodiversity	0.32	8.7
Weaknesses	Hard participation of small farms	0.31	5.5
	Difference between organic and ecological agriculture	0.31	5.5
	Often changes	0.37	6.5
Opportunities	Local heritage	0.33	6.0
	Public support	0.33	5.9
	Innovative business model	0.34	6.2
Threats	Climate changes	0.34	5.9
	Monoculture farming	0.35	7.5
	Expediency	0.31	7.2

The results of the evaluation show / see table. 3 / that three mechanisms have significant potential based on its strengths to successfully podmognat agricultural sector in the creation and maintenance of public goods. Summary of the strengths are high and close in value, indicating that the agricultural sector can count on support in implementing projects providing, both private and public benefits. Weaknesses

of mechanisms Water management and environmental payments are estimated to low ratings, which in addition to building on the strengths of their potential. The high general evaluation of the weaknesses of the mechanism protection of local, The traditional foods a mechanism more difficult to implement and achieve the benefits of its implementation. Three mechanisms show mirror results in terms of opportunities. With the great potential for utilization of opportunities is precisely the mechanism protection of local, traditional food, and the other two mechanisms are rated significantly lower. These mechanisms do they evaluate the potential to eliminate threats and improve conditions for the development of the agricultural sector to provide public goods.

Table 3. Potential mechanisms for support. Source: Own research, 2018

	Strengths	Weaknesses	Opportunities	Threats
	S	W	O	T
Water protection	7.92	5.76	5.86	7.46
Protection of local, traditional foods	8.40	7.47	6.83	5.70
Agro-environmental schemes	8.33	5.83	6.03	6.87

As a final result of the survey was conducted rating (prioritization) on six indicators for the implementation of the studied mechanisms. With the highest ratings stand Indicators - Effectiveness and Adoption, which sets expectations that mechanisms should give clear results themselves mechanisms should be recognized by, beneficiaries to realize their goals. Izmeraemostta the results achieved and targeted nature of the mechanisms are defined as intermediate in order of priority indicators for successful implementation of support mechanisms. The realization of hidden benefits and the need for additional costs associated with implementing the requirements of the mechanisms shall be determined by the lowest degree of importance.

Table 4. Rate of indicators for application of mechanisms. Source: Own research, 2018

No	Indicator	Total score
1.	Efficiency	4,654
2.	Adoption	4,276
3.	Measurability	3.792
4.	Focus	3.768
5.	Lower hidden cost	2,889
6.	Hidden benefits	2,809

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The applied research method allowed for a discussion in which depth were reviewed and analyzed three mechanisms to support the agricultural sector in the creation of public goods. Participants in the focus group, depending on their expertise and perspective rated various criteria, and brought the directions in which each mechanism has advantages or experiencing problems. Pelvic Based on the results of the study can be useful for improving the implementation of mechanisms and improving benefits for

the local community. The survey results give reason to be made the following important conclusions regarding the potential mechanisms to support the agricultural sector in the creation of public goods:

- mechanisms have strengths that can be used for the realization of the objectives in support of the agricultural sector to create public goods;
- implementation mechanisms is matched to a higher level of threats than opportunities;
- a need for the implementation of mechanisms to be more in line with high specificities of the different areas of impact;
- establishes a slight degree of interaction between the three investigated the mechanism;
- agricultural sector relies on the studied mechanisms have contributed to improving the economic situation of production structures;
- support of the local community is important, so that the potential of the studied mechanisms to be utilized fully.

The survey results show very large differences in the potential of the studied mechanisms. This determines the inability to balance the effects of their implementation in the context of territorial development. For this purpose it is necessary to develop and test scenarios, which are based on potential mechanisms for stimulating the creation of public goods and to achieve synergistic effects at regional level.

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